

Assessment of the protection of dopaminergic neurons by an $\alpha 7$ nicotinic receptor agonist, PHA 543613 using [18F]LBT-999 in a Parkinson's disease rat model

Sophie Sérrière¹, Aurélie Doméné¹, Johnny Vercouillie¹, Céline Mothes², Sylvie Bodard¹, Nuno Rodrigues³, Denis Guilloteau^{1, 4}, Sylvain Routier³, Guylène Page⁵, Sylvie Chalon^{1*}

¹UMR Inserm U930, Université François Rabelais de Tours, France, ²Laboratoires Cyclopharma, France, ³ICOA, UMR CNRS 7311, Université d'Orléans, France, ⁴CHRU Bretonneau, France, ⁵EA3808 CIMoThéMa, Université de Poitiers, France

Submitted to Journal:
Frontiers in Medicine

Specialty Section:
Nuclear Medicine

ISSN:
2296-858X

Article type:
Original Research in Medicine Article

Received on:
10 Jun 2015

Accepted on:
17 Aug 2015

Frontiers website link:
www.frontiersin.org

Citation:
Sérrière S, Doméné A, Vercouillie J, Mothes C, Bodard S, Rodrigues N, Guilloteau D, Routier S, Page G and Chalon S (2015) Assessment of the protection of dopaminergic neurons by an $\alpha 7$ nicotinic receptor agonist, PHA 543613 using [18F]LBT-999 in a Parkinson's disease rat model. *Front. Med.* 2:61. doi:10.3389/fmed.2015.00061

Copyright statement:
© 2015 Sérrière, Doméné, Vercouillie, Mothes, Bodard, Rodrigues, Guilloteau, Routier, Page and Chalon. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution License \(CC BY\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The use, distribution and reproduction in other forums is permitted, provided the original author(s) or licensor are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice. No use, distribution or reproduction is permitted which does not comply with these terms.

Provisional

1 **Assessment of the protection of dopaminergic neurons by an $\alpha 7$**
2 **nicotinic receptor agonist, PHA 543613 using [^{18}F]LBT-999 in a**
3 **Parkinson's disease rat model**

4 **Sophie Sérrière¹, Aurélie Doméné¹, Johnny Vercouillie¹, Céline Mothes², Sylvie Bodard¹, Nuno**
5 **Rodrigues³, Denis Guilloteau^{1,4}, Sylvain Routier³, Guylène Page⁵, Sylvie Chalon^{1*}**

6 ¹UMR Inserm U930, Université François Rabelais, Tours, France

7 ²Laboratoires Cyclopharma, Tours, France

8 ³Institut de Chimie Organique et Analytique, UMR CNRS 7311, Université d'Orléans, Orléans, France

9 ⁴CHRU Bretonneau, Tours, France

10 ⁵EA3808 CIMoThéMa, Université de Poitiers, Poitiers, France

11 * **Correspondence:** Dr. Sylvie Chalon, UMR Inserm U930, UFR de Médecine, 10 boulevard Tonnellé,
12 37032 Tours, France. sylvie.chalon@univ-tours.fr

13 **Keywords:** Autoradiography, dopamine transporter, 6-hydroxydopamine, neuroinflammation, PET,
14 **TSPO.**

15
16 **Abstract**

17
18 The inverse association between nicotine intake and Parkinson's Disease (PD) is well established and
19 suggests that this molecule could be neuroprotective through anti-inflammatory action mediated by
20 nicotinic receptors, including the $\alpha 7$ -subtype ($\alpha 7\text{R}$). The objective of this study was to evaluate the
21 effects of an agonist of $\alpha 7\text{R}$, PHA 543613, on striatal dopaminergic neurodegeneration and
22 neuroinflammation in a rat model of PD induced by 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) lesion. Adult
23 male Wistar rats were lesioned in the right striatum and assigned to either the PHA group (n=7) or
24 the Sham group (n=5). PHA 543613 hydrochloride at the concentration of 6 mg/kg (PHA group) or
25 vehicle (Sham group) was intra-peritoneally injected 2 hours before 6-OHDA lesioning and then at
26 days 2, 4 and 6 post-lesion. Positron emission tomography (PET) imaging was performed at 7 days
27 post-lesion using [^{18}F]LBT-999 to quantify the striatal dopamine transporter (DAT). After PET
28 imaging, neuroinflammation was evaluated in same animals in vitro through the measurement of the
29 microglial activation marker 18 kDa translocator protein (TSPO) by quantitative autoradiography
30 with [^3H]PK-11195. The DAT density reflecting the integrity of dopaminergic neurons was
31 significantly decreased while the intensity of neuroinflammation measured by TSPO density was
32 significantly increased in the lesioned compared to intact striatum in both groups. However, these
33 both modifications were partially reversed in the PHA group compared to Sham. In addition, a
34 significant positive correlation between the degree of lesion and the intensity of neuroinflammation
35 was evidenced. These findings indicate that PHA 543613 exerts neuroprotective effects on the striatal
36 dopaminergic neurons associated to a reduction in microglial activation in this model of PD. This
37 reinforces the hypothesis that an $\alpha 7\text{R}$ agonist could provide beneficial effects for the treatment of PD.

38
39 Number of words: 3337

40 Number of figures: 4

41
42
43

44 1. Introduction

45 Parkinson's disease (PD) is the second most common age-related neurodegenerative disorder after
46 Alzheimer's disease. It is characterized by the relatively selective death of dopaminergic neurons in
47 the substantia nigra pars compacta leading to a striatal dopamine deficit (1). PD is mainly sporadic
48 and is usually accompanied by motor symptoms such as bradykinesia, rigidity, postural instability
49 and resting tremor although a rising occurrence of non-motor symptoms is now recognized (2).
50 Currently, the treatment of PD is only symptomatic and no efficient neuroprotective or disease
51 modifying approaches are available. The search for such curative treatments requires to explore
52 various molecular pathways involved in order to focus on drugs able to block or curb disease
53 progression. One neuropathological feature of PD is the occurrence of neuroinflammatory processes
54 which manifests in part through the activation of microglial cell and astrocytes in the substantia nigra
55 (3, 4, 5). Regulating neuroinflammation appears therefore to be a potential therapeutic approach;
56 however, despite promising results obtained with different anti-inflammatory drugs in animal models
57 (6, 7), clinical studies have been disappointing (8).

58
59 As previously described in the peripheral nervous system (9), it has been shown that down-
60 regulation of the microglial activation can be induced through the activation of $\alpha 7$ nicotinic receptors
61 ($\alpha 7$ R) harbored by microglial cells (10). $\alpha 7$ R are the acetylcholine nicotinic receptors most
62 represented, with the $\alpha 4\beta 2$ subtype, in mammalian brain and have several pharmacological
63 characteristics such as a high permeability to calcium, low sensitivity to acetylcholine, and high
64 affinity for α -bungarotoxin (11). They are localized both on neurons (12) and glial cells (13). Besides
65 their effects on neurotransmission, $\alpha 7$ R are involved in the modulation of neuroinflammatory
66 processes, and agonists of these receptors are more efficient than acetylcholine at inhibiting the
67 inflammatory signaling and production of pro-inflammatory cytokines from immune cells (14). In
68 addition, several studies conducted in animal models support the idea that drugs acting at nicotinic
69 acetylcholine receptors may be beneficial for PD (15). In particular, it has recently been suggested
70 that the beneficial effect on the dopaminergic function observed with the $\alpha 7$ R agonist ABT-107 could
71 be linked to a reduction of the glutamate excitotoxicity leading to the promotion of neuronal integrity
72 (16)

73
74 In this study, we used a selective agonist of $\alpha 7$ R, PHA 543613 (17, 18), in a rat model of PD induced
75 by unilateral striatal administration of 6-hydroxydopamine (6-OHDA) to investigate whether this
76 compound has a protective effect on dopaminergic neurons through an anti-inflammatory
77 mechanism. For this aim, we measured the striatal dopamine transporter (DAT) by in vivo PET
78 imaging using the fluorinated derivative of PE2I, (*E*)-*N*-(4-fluorobut-2-enyl) 2β -carbomethoxy- 3β -(4'-
79 tolyl)nortropine or LBT-999 that we previously developed (19, 20). The neuroinflammation was
80 evaluated through the density of the 18 kDa translocator protein (TSPO) using a quantitative
81 autoradiographic method with the reference ligand of TSPO [3 H]PK-11195 which has been widely
82 used in rodent and human brains (21, 22, 23, 24).

84 2. Materials and methods

85 2.1 Animals

86
87 All procedures were conducted in accordance with the European Community Council Directive
88 2010/63/EU for laboratory animal care and the experimental protocol was validated by the Regional
89 Ethical Committee (Authorization N°00434.02). Experiments were carried out on adult male Wistar

rats (CERJ, France) weighing 290-300 g at the beginning of experiments. Animals were housed in groups of 2 per cage in a temperature ($21 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) and humidity ($55 \pm 5\%$) controlled environment under a 12-hour light/dark cycle, with food and water available ad libitum.

2.2 6-OHDA lesion

The experimental design was performed according to a previously described procedure (25). Twenty minutes before surgery, rats were injected intra-peritoneally with pargyline (50 mg/kg, Sigma, Saint-Quentin Fallavier, France). Rats were anesthetized with isoflurane (4%, 500 mL/min) and placed on a stereotaxic apparatus (Stoelting, Phymep, Paris, France) and maintained under isoflurane 2.5% (500 mL/min) during surgery. The skull was exposed and small holes were made with a dental drill. Lesion was carried out by unilateral intrastriatal injection of 6-OHDA hydrochloride (1 mg/mL, Tocris Bioscience, Bristol, UK). A total of 10 μg of 6-OHDA was administered in 2 areas of the right striatum (1 mg/mL in 0.01% ascorbic acid, pH 4.5, i.e., 5 μg in 5 μL for each area) with a Hamilton syringe (gauge 25, Hamilton, Massy, France) at a flow rate of 1 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. Coordinates from bregma were AP = +0.5 mm, L = -2.5 mm, P = -5 mm, and AP = -0.5 mm, L = -4 mm, P = -5 mm according to Paxinos and Watson atlas (26). The needle was left in place for 4 minutes after injection and then removed slowly to optimize toxin diffusion. After surgery, the rats were given buprenorphine (0.05 mg/kg sub-cutaneously) for postoperative pain and were allowed to recover from surgery for 7 days before being subjected to the imaging experiments.

2.3 Treatment with the $\alpha 7$ receptor agonist PHA 543613

PHA 543613 hydrochloride (Tocris Bioscience, Bristol, UK; 17, 18) was dissolved in sterile water and intra-peritoneally injected at the concentration of 6 mg/kg (300 $\mu\text{l}/300\text{ g}$ body weight) 2 hours before 6-OHDA lesioning and then at days 2, 4 and 6 post-lesion (cumulative dose of 24 mg/kg). Twelve rats were included in this study and separated into 2 groups as follows: 7 lesioned rats received the treatment (PHA group) and 5 lesioned rats received intra-peritoneally injection of vehicle at the same time points (Sham group).

2.4 Preparation of the tracer

No-carrier-added [^{18}F]LBT-999 was prepared as previously described (27). The tracer was produced via direct nucleophilic substitution from its chloro analog by adding 3 mg of the precursor in 1 mL of DMSO to the dry [^{18}F] KF/K_{2.2.2} complex. After heating at 165°C for 10 minutes, the mixture was cooled and purified by HPLC (Alltima, C18, 250 x 10 mm, 5 μm column) using ammonium acetate 0.1M/acetonitrile 4/6 as the mobile phase at a 4 mL/min flow rate. In these conditions, time retention was 13.5 minutes. The desired fraction was collected, diluted in water, and the [^{18}F]LBT-999 was trapped on a *t*-C18 light SepPak cartridge. The cartridge was rinsed with 5 mL of injectable water, and the [^{18}F]LBT-999 was eluted with 0.5 mL of ethanol. Formulation was completed by the addition of 3.5 mL of NaCl 0.9%. Quality control was performed by HPLC (Alltima, C18, 250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μm column) using ammonium acetate 0.1M/Acetonitrile 3/7. [^{18}F]LBT-999 was obtained with a radiochemical purity >98% and with a mean specific activity of $65 \pm 10\text{ GBq}/\mu\text{mol}$.

2.5 PET imaging and data analyses

Positron emission tomography (PET) imaging was performed at 7 days post-lesion. Acquisitions were made on a microPET eXplore VISTA-CT system (GE Healthcare, France) which has an effective axial/trans axial field of view (FOV) of 4.8/6.7 cm, a spatial resolution less than 2 mm and a

139 sensitivity above 2.5% in the whole FOV. Animals were anesthetized with isoflurane (Baxter,
140 France), at 4-5% in O₂ for induction and then 1.5-2% during scanning. For imaging, each rat was
141 placed on a thermo-regulated bed (Minerve, France) in the prone position with a nose cone. The brain
142 was positioned on the center of the FOV. Before PET acquisition, a 5-minute computed tomography
143 (CT) scan was acquired for attenuation correction. A bolus injection of 37 MBq/300 g body weight
144 of [¹⁸F]LBT-999 in saline was administered into the tail vein. During PET acquisition, the respiratory
145 rate and body temperature were monitored and kept as constant as possible. Each acquisition lasted
146 50 minutes and PET list-mode scans were rebinned into 27 frames: 4 10-seconds frames followed by
147 4 20-seconds frames, 4 60-seconds frames, 14 180-seconds frames, and 1 of 120-seconds frame.
148 Each PET scan was corrected for random, scatter, and attenuation, and the images were reconstructed
149 using a 2-D OSEM algorithm (GE Healthcare, France) into voxels of 0.3875 × 0.3875 × 0.775 mm³.
150 All images were analyzed using PMOD (3.403, PMOD Technologies, Zurich, Switzerland,
151 www.pmod.com). The PET-corrected images were used for standard uptake value (SUV)
152 calculations. For each PET scan, data were summed over the first 5 minutes after radiotracer injection
153 to create a pseudo perfusion image. This image reflects the initial flow-dependent activity and was
154 registered with the CT image through a known hardware registration (PET to CT transformation). CT
155 scans were also recorded using a rat brain magnetic resonance imaging template (MRI-Template)
156 (PMOD) (28) and a rat brain MRI-Template to CT transformation was saved. All PET images, after
157 checking for potential head movements, were co-registered in a single interpolation to the Schiffer rat
158 brain MRI Template by a combination of these 2 transformations (MRI Template to CT, and PET to
159 CT transformations). The inverse combined transformation was calculated. The Schiffer MRI
160 template was processed in the PET space images using the inverse transformation applied on the
161 originals dynamic PET data and statistics for the regions of interest (ROIs) were extracted. PET
162 images were analyzed with the ROIs for the left striatum (i.e. intact striatum, IST), right striatum
163 (i.e., lesioned striatum, LST), and cerebellum (CE). In this study, the standard uptake value ratio
164 (SUVr) was used as quantitative criterions. All SUVrs were calculated using the CE as the reference
165 region.

167 2.6 Autoradiographic study

168
169 After the PET scan, rats were humanely killed by decapitation under light isoflurane anesthesia, and
170 their brains carefully removed on ice for autoradiographic experiments according to (25). Brains
171 were frozen in isopentane cooled at -35°C and stored at -80°C. Coronal brain sections 20-μm thick
172 were cut with a cryostat (CM 3050S, Leica, Germany) at -20°C, collected on gelatinized slides and
173 stored at -80°C for at least 4 days. A total of 6 sections per brain were studied for each animal. The
174 density of TSPO binding sites was measured by in vitro autoradiographic experiments using [³H]PK-
175 11195 (specific activity 3.06 GBq/μmol; Perkin Elmer, Norwalk, CT) at 1 nmol/L in a 50-mmol/L
176 Tris HCL buffer pH 7.4. Brain sections were allowed to equilibrate at room temperature (RT) for 3
177 hours, then were incubated with 1 nmol/L [³H]PK-11195 in 50 mmol/L Tris-HCl buffer pH 7.4 at RT
178 for 60 minutes. Non-specific binding was assessed in the presence of 1 μmol/L PK-11195 (Sigma
179 Aldrich, France). Sections were rinsed twice in ice cold buffer (4°C) for 5 minutes, then briefly in
180 distilled water at 4°C and dried at RT. Dry sections were made conductive by an application of metal
181 electric tape (3 M, Euromedex) on the free side and then placed in the gas chamber of the β-imagerTM
182 2000 (Biospace Lab, Paris, France). Acquisitions were collected for 4 hours. Two anatomical ROIs,
183 i.e. the LST and IST were selected manually and identified in Paxinos and Watson atlas (26). Using
184 the β-vision software (Biospace Lab, Paris, France), the level of bound radioactivity was directly
185 determined by counting the number of β-particles emitted from the delineated area. The radioligand
186 signal in the ROIs was measured for each rat and expressed as counts per minute per square
187 millimeter (cpm/mm²). Specific binding was determined by subtracting non-specific binding from

188 total binding. Radioactivity was quantified using an image analyzer (M3-vision Biospace
189 Instruments, France). The percentage increase of TSPO binding in LST versus IST was calculated as:

$$\frac{[LST - IST]}{IST} * 100$$

190 2.7 Statistical analysis

191

192 For PET imaging and autoradiographic studies, results were expressed as mean \pm mean standard error
193 (SEM). Comparisons between the binding in the LST and IST were performed using the Wilcoxon
194 test one-tailed. To compare the 2 groups of rats (PHA vs. Sham), a Mann-Whitney test was used. The
195 level of significance was $p \leq 0.05$. Correlation between PET imaging and autoradiography was
196 estimated by using a one-tailed Spearman test (GraphPad InStat, GraphPad Software, San Diego,
197 Calif). The level of significance was $p \leq 0.05$. Statistical analyses were performed using the
198 GraphPad Prism software version 5.

199

200 3. Results

201 3.1 Animals

202

203 No physiological issues and no difference in body weight were observed between animals in the
204 PHA and Sham groups (weight on the day of lesion: 300 ± 4 vs. 297 ± 6 g, respectively; weight at
205 day 7 post-lesion: 313 ± 5 vs. 301 ± 6 g, respectively).

206

207 3.2 PET imaging

208

209 PET images are presented in Figure 1. After [^{18}F]LBT-999 injection, a progressive accumulation of
210 radioactivity was observed mainly in the IST (Figure 1A). Static PET images revealed that
211 accumulation of [^{18}F]LBT999 on the lesioned striatum was greater in PHA rats than in Sham rats
212 (Figures 1B and 1C).

213 The time activity curves (Figure 2A) showed a rapid uptake of [^{18}F]LBT-999 in the ROIs (i.e., the
214 IST, LST, and CE) after intravenous bolus injection. In the CE, the uptake decreased rapidly and
215 remained low and stable after 20 minutes post-injection in both groups (SUV in the PHA group: 0.97
216 ± 0.06 and 0.99 ± 0.08 in the Sham group). The uptake remained high and stable in the IST in both
217 groups (SUV PHA: 3.99 ± 0.33 and 3.84 ± 0.31 in the Sham group). By contrast, the values observed
218 in the LST were reduced in comparison to those in the IST in both groups (SUV PHA 1.41 ± 0.19
219 and 0.98 ± 0.11 in the Sham group).

220 The analysis of SUVr to CE (Figure 2B) showed a significant reduction in the LST compared to the
221 IST, both in the PHA (1.58 ± 0.23 vs. 4.34 ± 0.42 , $p < 0.05$ Wilcoxon test) and Sham (0.99 ± 0.07 vs
222 3.94 ± 0.37 , $p < 0.05$ Wilcoxon test) groups. These SUVr were similar in the IST in both groups
223 (PHA: 4.34 ± 0.42 and Sham: 3.94 ± 0.37), whereas in the LST the SUVr was slightly higher in the
224 PHA than in the Sham group (1.58 ± 0.23 and 0.99 ± 0.07 , respectively). In addition, the percentage
225 of decrease in the SUVr (which reflects the intensity of the lesion) was significantly lower in the
226 PHA group compared to the Sham group (64.6 ± 2.9 vs $73.7 \pm 3.7\%$, $p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney test)
227 (Figure 2C).

228

229 3.3 Autoradiographic study

230

231 The TSPO density was evaluated on adjacent brain sections by [^3H]PK-11195 binding in the IST and
232 LST from each rat in both groups as illustrated in Figure 3A. The specific binding of [^3H]PK-11195

233 (Figure 3B) in the IST was low and similar between the PHA and Sham groups (1.53 ± 0.18 and 1.40
234 ± 0.29 cpm/mm², respectively). In the LST of both groups, this binding was significantly increased
235 (PHA group: 3.69 ± 0.32 vs 1.53 ± 0.18 cpm/mm² in the IST $p < 0.05$ Wilcoxon test; Sham group:
236 4.85 ± 0.29 vs 1.40 ± 0.06 cpm/mm² in the IST, $p < 0.05$ Wilcoxon test). However, this increase was
237 significantly lower in the PHA group than in the Sham group (24% lower, $p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney
238 test). In addition, as shown in Figure 3C, the percent of increase of TSPO binding in LST vs. IST was
239 significantly lower in the PHA group compared to the Sham group ($157.5 \pm 30.9\%$ vs. $262.2 \pm$
240 20.6% , $p < 0.05$, Mann-Whitney test).

241

242 3.4 Correlation between PET imaging and autoradiography

243

244 The correlation between PET imaging results (expressed as the degree of lesion, i.e., % tracer binding
245 in LST vs. IST) and autoradiography (expressed as a percent of neuroinflammation, i.e., % TSPO
246 binding in LST vs. IST) is shown in Figure 4. The degree of lesion measured by PET imaging was
247 positively correlated with the intensity of neuroinflammation ($p = 0.05$, $\rho = 0.49$).

248

249 4. Discussion

250 To date no treatment has been recognized as useful neuroprotective approach for PD.
251 Neuroinflammation is believed to be a key pathophysiological mechanism that could be targeted to
252 achieve neuroprotection (29). A number of epidemiological and experimental evidence have
253 converged to demonstrate a neuroprotective effect of nicotine in PD (30), involving particularly the
254 $\alpha 7$ subtype of nicotinic receptors (31). Interestingly, this effect could be at least partly mediated by
255 the modulation of neuroinflammation affected by these receptors (11). On this basis, we evaluated in
256 this study the effects of a potent agonist of $\alpha 7R$, PHA 543613, on the neurodegeneration of
257 dopaminergic neurons and associated microglial activation in a rat model of PD.

258 To date, little is known on the potential effects of $\alpha 7R$ agonists in PD. As we aimed to induce a
259 potential neuroprotective effect, we used a partial lesion model which corresponds to an early
260 symptomatic stage of PD (32, 33).

261

262 Because the striatal dopamine transporter (DAT) has proven to be a marker that correlates with the
263 level of dopaminergic denervation (30, 34), we studied the integrity of striatal dopaminergic nerve
264 endings using PET imaging with the fluorinated derivative of PE2I, (*E*)-*N*-(4-fluorobut-2-enyl)2 β -
265 carbomethoxy-3 β -(4'-tolyl)nortropane or LBT-999 that we previously developed (19, 20). We
266 recently demonstrated the ability of [¹⁸F]LBT-999 to quantify in vivo the DAT in the rat brain with
267 high reproducibility, sensitivity, and specificity (27). In addition, this tracer has proven useful in a rat
268 model of PD, to quantify the lesions and as a treatment for cell restoration (35).

269 In order to evaluate the effects of PHA on neuroinflammation, we measured the density of the 18
270 kDa translocator protein (TSPO) in the brain of PD rats after exploration by PET imaging. Indeed,
271 the inflammatory reaction in the brain involves the activation of microglia (36) leading to a dramatic
272 increase in the expression of the TSPO which can thus be considered as a sensitive biomarker of this
273 activation (37, 38). We used a quantitative autoradiographic method with the reference ligand of
274 TSPO [³H]PK-11195 which has been widely used in rodent and human brains (21, 22, 23, 24).

275

276 Our PET experiment showed that at 7 days after 6-OHDA lesion, the specific accumulation of
277 [¹⁸F]LBT-999 in the striatum, measured as the SUV_r to cerebellum as reference region, was high and
278 similar on the intact side of all animals, and reduced on the lesioned side, as expected. However, we
279 observed that the degree of lesion of dopaminergic neurons on the lesioned side, calculated as the

280 percentage of tracer binding in the lesioned versus intact striatum was slightly but significantly
281 reduced in the PHA treated group compared to Sham group (64 vs. 74% lesion, respectively). These
282 results are in agreement with a partial neuroprotective effect of the $\alpha 7R$ agonist on dopaminergic
283 nerve endings. It is known that PHA 543613 is a potent and selective $\alpha 7R$ agonist (17, 18), which has
284 been shown to reduce induced brain edema in a mouse model through the inhibition of GSK-3 β (39,
285 40). Similarly, PHA 568487, an $\alpha 7R$ agonist closely related to PHA 543613, has been shown to
286 reduce the severity of an ischemic stroke (41).

287
288 In rodent models of PD, neuroprotective effects have already been described with different $\alpha 7R$
289 agonists, i.e. DMXBA (42), PNU-282987 (43) and more recently ABT-107 (16). In several of these
290 studies microglial activation was reduced by treatment with $\alpha 7R$ agonists, but the effects on
291 neuroinflammatory parameters were observed at much earlier time's post-lesion than the effects on
292 dopaminergic parameters (42, 43). We demonstrated herein a strong relationship between the effects
293 of the $\alpha 7R$ agonist on the dopaminergic neurons integrity and on neuroinflammation, because $\alpha 7R$
294 agonist treatment reduced both dopaminergic neuron loss and microglial activation in the same
295 animal. This is reinforced by the fact that we showed a significant positive correlation between the
296 decrease of [^{18}F]LBT-999 accumulation and [3H]PK-11195 binding, which confirms that the
297 upregulation of TSPO is directly correlated with the degree of neuronal damage (38).

298
299 Taking into account the small number of animals studied, our present findings can be considered as
300 preliminary. In addition, several complementary experiments such as the evaluation of dopaminergic
301 neuron integrity through TH immunostaining, behavioral tests assessing the dopaminergic function
302 and different experimental designs with various doses and administration points would be performed
303 to confirm our findings. Nevertheless, we showed that in vivo PET exploration in rodent models can
304 be useful to evaluate different neuroprotective approaches using a variety of pharmacological
305 compounds and experimental designs. In this field, the use of the TSPO PET tracer [^{18}F]DPA-714 in
306 parallel to PET tracers of neurodegeneration would be of great value in rodent models of
307 neurodegenerative disease, as recently done (44).

308
309 Our findings indicate that PHA 543613, a high affinity and selective $\alpha 7R$ agonist, partially preserved
310 the integrity of striatal dopaminergic nerve endings and reduced neuroinflammation in 6-OHDA-
311 lesioned rats. This reinforces the hypothesis that $\alpha 7R$ agonists may be beneficial in Parkinson's
312 disease.

313 **Conflict of interest:** The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

314 **Non-standard abbreviations:** $\alpha 7$ -nicotinic receptor: $\alpha 7R$, LST: lesioned striatum, IST: intact
315 striatum, CE: cerebellum, SUV: standard uptake value, SUVr: standard uptake value ratio to CE.

316 Acknowledgments

317 The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's
318 Seventh Framework Programme (FP7/2007-2013) under grant agreement n°278850 (INMiND) and
319 from Labex IRON (ANR-11-LABX-18-01).

320 We thank the Laboratoires Cyclopharma for providing fluor-18.

321 References

- 322 1. Dauer W, Przedborski S. Parkinson's disease: mechanisms and models. *Neuron* (2003) **39**:889-
323 909. doi:10.1016/S0896-6273(03)00568-3
- 324 2. Ferrer I, Lopez-Gonzalez I, Carmona M, Dalfo E, Pujol A, Martinez A. Neurochemistry and the
325 non-motor aspects of PD. *Neurobiol Dis* (2012) **46**:508-526. doi:10.1016/j.nbd.2011.10.019
- 326 3. McGeer PL, Itagaki S, Boyes BE, McGeer EG. Reactive microglia are positive for HLA-DR in the
327 substantia nigra of Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease brains. *Neurology* (1988) **38**:1285-
328 1291
- 329 4. Hartmann A, Hunot S, Hirsch EC. Inflammation and dopaminergic neuronal loss in Parkinson's
330 disease: a complex matter. *Exp Neurol* (2003) **184**:561-564.
331 doi:10.1016/j.expneurol.2003.08.004
- 332 5. Lee JK, Tran T, Taney MG. Neuroinflammation in Parkinson's disease. *J Neuroimmune*
333 *Pharmacol* (2009) **4**:419-429. doi:10.1007/s11481-009-9176-0
- 334 6. Aubin N, Curet O, Deffois A, Carter C. Aspirin and salicylate protect against MPTP-induced
335 dopamine depletion in mice. *J Neurochem* (1998) **71**:1635-1642. doi:10.1046/j.1471-
336 4159.1998.71041635.x
- 337 7. Teismann P, Ferger B. Inhibition of the cyclooxygenase isoenzymes COX-1 and COX-2 provide
338 neuroprotection in the MPTP-mouse model of Parkinson's disease. *Synapse* (2001) **39**:167-
339 174.
- 340 8. Tansey MG, Goldberg MS. Neuroinflammation in Parkinson's disease: its role in neuronal death
341 and implications for therapeutic intervention. *Neurobiol Dis* (2010) **37**:510-518.
342 doi:10.1016/j.nbd.2009.11.004
- 343 9. Wang H, Yu M, Ochani M, Amella CA, Tanovic M, Susarla S, et al. Nicotinic acetylcholine
344 receptor $\alpha 7$ subunit is an essential regulator of inflammation. *Nature* (2003) **421**:384-388.
345 doi:10.1038/nature01339
- 346 10. Shytle RD, Mori T, Townsend K, Vendrame M, Sun N, Zeng J, et al. Cholinergic modulation of
347 microglial activation by $\alpha 7$ nicotinic receptors. *J Neurochem* (2004) **89**:337-343.
348 doi:10.1046/j.1471-4159.2004.02347.x
- 349 11. Connejero-Goldberg C, Davies P, Ulloa L. Alpha7 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor: a link
350 between inflammation and neurodegeneration. *Neurosci Biobehav Rev* (2008) **32**:693-706.
351 doi:10.1016/j.neubiorev.2007.10.007
- 352 12. Jensen AA, Frolund B, Liljefors T, Krogsgaard-Larsen P. Neuronal nicotinic acetylcholine
353 receptors: structural revelations, target identifications, and therapeutic inspirations. *J Med*
354 *Chem* (2005) **48**:4705-4745. doi:10.1021/jm040219e
- 355 13. Gahring LC, Persiyanov K, Dunn D, Weiss R, Meyer EL, Rogers SW. Mouse strain-specific
356 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor expression by inhibitory interneurons and astrocytes in the
357 dorsal hippocampus. *J Comp Neurol* (2004) **468**:334-346. doi:10.1002/cne.1094
- 358 14. De Longe WJ, Ulloa L. The alpha7 nicotinic acetylcholine receptor as a pharmacological target
359 for inflammation. *Br J Pharmacol* (2007) **151**:915-929. doi:10.1038/sj.bjp.0707264
- 360 15. Quik M, Campos C, Grady SR. Multiple CNS nicotinic receptors mediate L-dopa-induced
361 dyskinesias: studies with parkinsonian nicotinic receptor knockout mice. *Biochem Pharmacol*
362 (2013) **868**:1153-1162. doi:10.1016/j.bcp.2013.06.027
- 363 16. Bordia T, McGregor M, Papke RL, Decker MW, McIntosh JM, Quik M. The $\alpha 7$ nicotinic
364 receptor ABT-107 protects against nigrostriatal damage in rats with unilateral 6-
365 hydroxydopamine lesions. *Exp Neurol* (2015) **263**:277-284.
366 doi:10.1016/j.expneurol.2014.09.015
- 367 17. Wishka DG, Walker DP, Yates KM, Reitz SC, Jia S, Myers JK, et al. Discovery of *N*-[(3*R*)-1-
368 Azabicyclo[2.2.2]oct-3-yl][2,3-*c*]pyridine-5-carboxamide, an agonist of the $\alpha 7$ nicotinic
369 acetylcholine receptor, for the potential treatment of cognitive deficits in schizophrenia:

- 370 synthesis and structure-activity relationship. *J Med Chem* (2006) **49**:4425-4436.
371 doi:10.1021/jm0602413
- 372 18. Acker BA, Jacobsen EJ, Rogers BN, Wishka DG, Reitz SC, Piotrowski DW. Discovery of *N*-
373 [(3*R*,5*R*)-1-azabicyclo[3.2.1]oct-3-yl]furo-[2,3-*c*]pyridine-5-carboxamide a an agonist of the
374 $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor: in vitro and in vivo activity. *Bioorg Med Chem* (2008)
375 **18**:3611-3615. doi:10.1016/j.bmcl.2008.04.070
- 376 19. Chalon S, Hall H, Saba W, Garreau L, Dollé F, Halldin C, et al. Pharmacological characterization
377 of (E)-*N*-(4-fluorobut-2-enyl)-2beta-carbomethoxy-3beta-(4'-tolyl)nortropane (LBT-999) as a
378 highly promising fluorinated ligand for the dopamine transporter. *J Pharmacol Exp Ther*
379 (2006) **317**:147-152. doi:10.1124/jpet.105.096792
- 380 20. Dollé F, Helfenbein J, Hinnen F, Mavel S, Mincheva Z, Saba W, et al. One-step radiosynthesis of
381 [¹⁸F]LBT-999: a selective radioligand for the visualization of the dopamine transporter with
382 PET. *J. Labelled Compd Rad* (2007) **50**:716-723. doi:10.1002/jlcr.1412
- 383 21. Doble A, Malgouri C, Daniel M, Daniel N, Imbault F, Basbaum A. et al. Labelling of peripheral-
384 type benzodiazepine binding sites in human brain with [³H]PK 11195: anatomical and
385 subcellular distribution. *Brain Res Bull* (1987) **18**:49-64. doi:10.1016/0361-9230(87)90033-5
- 386 22. Dubois A, Bénavidès J, Peny B, Duverger D, Fage D, Gotti B, et al. Imaging of primary and
387 remote ischaemic and excitotoxic brain lesions. An autoradiographic study of peripheral type
388 benzodiazepine binding sites in the rat and cat. *Brain Res* (1988) **445**:77-90.
389 doi:10.1016/0006-8993(88)91076-1
- 390 23. Myers R, Manjil LG, Cullen BM, Price GW, Frackowiak RS, Cremer JE. Macrophage and
391 astrocyte populations in relation to [³H]PK-11195 binding in rat cerebral cortex following a
392 local ischaemic lesion. *J Cereb Blood Flow Metab* (1991) **11**:314-322.
393 doi:10.1038/jcbfm.1991.64
- 394 24. Miller TR, Wetter JB, Jarvis MF, Bitner RS. Spinal microglial activation in rat models of
395 neuropathic and osteoarthritic pain: an autoradiographic study using [³H]PK11195. *Eur J*
396 *Pain* (2013) **17**:692-703. doi:10.1002/j.1532-2149.2012.00232.x
- 397 25. Maia S, Arlicot N, Vierron E, Bodard S, Vergote J, Guilloteau D, et al. Longitudinal and parallel
398 monitoring of neuroinflammation and neurodegeneration in a 6-hydroxydopamine rat model
399 of Parkinson's disease. *Synapse* (2012) **66**:573-83. doi:10.1002/syn.21543
- 400 26. Paxinos G, Watson C. *The Rat Brain in Stereotaxic Coordinates*. San Diego (6th ed): Elsevier
401 Academic Press (2007).
- 402 27. Sérière S, Tauber C, Vercouillie J, Guilloteau D, Deloye JB, Garreau L, et al. In vivo PET
403 quantification of the dopamine transporter in rat brain with [¹⁸F]LBT-999. *Nucl Med Biol*
404 (2014) **41**:106-13. doi:10.1016/j.nucmedbio.2013.09.007
- 405 28. Schiffer WK, Mirrione MM, Dewey SL. Optimizing experimental protocols for quantitative
406 behavioral imaging with 18F-FDG in rodents. *J Nucl Med* (2007) **48**:277-87.
- 407 29. Athauda D, Foltynie T. The ongoing pursuit of neuroprotective therapies in Parkinson disease.
408 *Nat Rev Neurol* (2015) **11**:25-40. doi:10.1038/nrneurol.2014.226
- 409 30. Quik M, O'Neill M, Perez XA. Nicotine neuroprotection against nigrostriatal damage:
410 importance of the animal model. *Trends Pharmacol Sci* (2007) **28**:229-235.
411 doi:org/10.1016/j.tips.2007.03.001
- 412 31. Quik M, Perez XA, Bordia T. Nicotine as a potential neuroprotective agent for Parkinson's
413 disease. *Mov Dis* (2012) **27**:947-957. doi:10.1002/mds.25028
- 414 32. Björklund A, Rosenblad C, Winkler C, Kirik D. Studies on neuroprotective and regenerative
415 effects of GDNF in a partial lesion model of parkinson's disease. *Neurobiol Dis* (1997) **4**:186-
416 200. doi:10.1006/nbdi.1997.0151

- 417 33. Kirik D, Rosenblad C, Björklund A. Characterization of behavioral and neurodegenerative
418 changes following partial lesions of the nigrostriatal dopamine system induced by intrastriatal
419 6-hydroxydopamine in the rat. *Exp Neurol* (1998) **152**:259-277. doi:10.1006/exnr.1998.6848
- 420 34. Brooks DJ, Pavese N. Imaging biomarkers in Parkinson' disease. *Progr Neurobiol* (2011)
421 **95**:614-628. doi:10.1016/j.pneurobio.2011.08.009
- 422 35. Grealish S, Diguët E, Kirkeby A, Mattson B, Heuer A, Bramouille Y, et al. Human ESC-derived
423 dopamine neurons show similar preclinical efficacy and potency to fetal neurons when grafted
424 in a rat model of Parkinson's disease. *Cell Stem Cell* (2014) **15**:653-665.
425 doi:10.1016/j.stem.2014.09.017
- 426 36. Kreutzberg GW. Microglia: a sensor for pathological events in the CNS. *Trends Neurosci* (1996)
427 **19**:312-318. doi:10.1016/0166-2236(96)10049-7
- 428 37. Papadopoulos V, Baraldi M, Guilarte TR, Knudsen TB, Lacapère JJ, Lindemann P, et al.
429 Translocator protein (18 kDa): new nomenclature for the peripheral-type benzodiazepine
430 receptor based on its structure and molecular function. *Trends Pharmacol Sci* (2006) **27**:402-
431 409. doi:10.1016/j.tips.2006.06.005
- 432 38. Chen MK, Guilarte TR. Translocator protein 18 kDa (TSPO): molecular sensor of brain injury
433 and repair. *Pharmacol Ther* (2008) **118**:1-17. doi:10.1016/j.pharmthera.2007.12.004
- 434 39. Krafft PR, Altay O, Rolland WB, Duri K, Lekic T, Tang J, et al. $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine
435 receptor agonism confers neuroprotection through GSK-3 β inhibition in a mouse model of
436 intracerebral hemorrhage. *Stroke* (2012) **43**:844-850. doi:
437 10.1161/STROKEAHA.111.639989
- 438 40. Krafft PR, Caner B, Klebe D, Rolland WB, Tang J, Zhang JH. *Stroke* (2013) **44**:1743-1747.
439 doi:10.1161/STROKEAHA.111.000427
- 440 41. Han Z, Shen F, He Y, Degos V, Camus M, Maze M, et al. Activation of $\alpha 7$ nicotinic
441 acetylcholine receptor reduces ischemic stroke injury through reduction of pro-inflammatory
442 macrophages and oxidative stress. *PLOS one* (2014) **9**:e105711.
443 doi:10.1371/journal.pone.0105711
- 444 42. Suzuki S, Kaamata J, Matsushita T, Matumura A, Hisahara S, Takata K, et al. 3-[(2,4-
445 dimethoxy)benzylidene]-anabaseine dihydrochloride protects against 6-hydroxydopamine-
446 induced parkinsonian neurodegeneration through $\alpha 7$ nicotinic acetylcholine receptor
447 stimulation in rats. *J Neurosci* (2013) **91**:462-471. doi:10.1002/jnr.23160
- 448 43. Stuckenholz V, Bacher M, Balzer-Geletzer M, Alvarez-Fischer D, Oertel WH, Dodel RC, et al.
449 The $\alpha 7$ nAChR agonist PNU-282987 reduces inflammation and MPTP-induced nigral
450 dopaminergic cell loss in mice. *J Park Dis* (2013) **3**:161-172. doi: 10.3233/JPD-120157
- 451 44. Sérière S, Tauber C, Vercouillie J, Mothes C, Pruckner C, Guilloteau D, et al. Amyloid load and
452 translocator protein 18 kDa in APP^{swe}PS1-dE9 mice: a longitudinal study. *Neurobiol Aging*
453 (2015) **36**:1639-1652. doi:10.1016/j.neurobiolaging.2014.11.023

454 **Figure legends**

455 **Figure 1: PET brain images with [¹⁸F]LBT-999.** (A) Coronal PET images in a 6-OHDA lesioned
456 rat with [¹⁸F]LBT-999 from 1.8 to 50 minutes after bolus injection of the tracer. PET brain static
457 sagittal and coronal images with [¹⁸F]LBT-999 co-registered with the MRI-Template in a Sham rat
458 (B) and in a PHA rat (C).

459
460 **Figure 2: Quantitative results from PET brain images with [¹⁸F]LBT-999.** (A) Mean-time
461 activity curves of [¹⁸F]LBT-999 SUVs in the IST, LST, and CE, in Sham (blue) and PHA (red) rats.
462 (B) Mean-time activity curves of SUVr to CE of tracer accumulation in IST and LST in Sham (blue)
463 and PHA (red) rats. (C) Percentage of lesion in Sham (blue) and PHA (red) rats. *p<0.05 compared
464 with Sham (Mann-Whitney test). Abbreviations: CE: cerebellum, IST: intact striatum, LST: lesioned
465 striatum, SUV: standard uptake value, SUVr: standard uptake value ratio to CE.

466
467 **Figure 3: Autoradiographic analysis of TSPO density with [³H]PK-11195.** (A) Representative
468 total (left side) and non-specific (right side) binding of [³H]PK-11195 obtained on 20 µm-thick
469 coronal brain sections in Sham rats (upper panel) and in PHA rats (lower panel). Note that the
470 cortical signal reflects the binding resulting from the mechanical lesion induced by the needle. (B)
471 Quantitative autoradiographic measurements of TSPO density expressed as specific binding of
472 [³H]PK-11195 in IST and LST from Sham (blue) and PHA (red) rats (mean cpm/mm² ± SEM). (C)
473 Percentage of TSPO binding in LST versus IST (mean ± SEM%) from Sham (blue) and PHA (red)
474 rats.*p<0.05 (Mann-Whitney test). #p<0.05 (Wilcoxon test). Abbreviations: TSPO: translocator
475 protein, IST: intact striatum, LST: lesioned striatum.

476
477 **Figure 4: Correlation between PET imaging and autoradiography.** The correlation is reported for
478 both groups. Sham rats are represented in blue and PHA rats are in red. A one-tailed Spearman test
479 was used (p = 0.05, rho = 0.49).

Figure 1.TIF

Figure 2.TIF

Figure 3.TIF

Figure 4.TIF

